

Determining optimal conditions for obtaining graphene oxide in ammonium carbonate solution by electrochemical method

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ABSTRACT

At present, many studies are being conducted on obtaining graphene oxide from graphite by chemical and electrochemical methods. However, the purification of graphene oxide obtained by these methods from the reaction mixture has certain complications. In our study, the possibility of obtaining and purifying graphene oxide of ammonium carbonate by electrochemical method was shown. The optimal conditions for obtaining graphene oxide at different concentrations of ammonium carbonate solution and different electric voltages were studied. The results showed that in ammonium carbonate solution, with a concentration of 1 mol/L, was found to be an optimal condition for obtaining a relatively productive amount of graphene oxide by passing an electric current from graphite electrodes at a voltage of 6 V.

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1. Introduction

The unique properties of materials based on graphene and graphene oxide (GO) attract many scientists. Because graphene-based materials are characterized by a large surface area, unique electrical properties, unique mechanical properties and other aspects [1-3]. The main raw material of graphene and GO is graphite, which is important because it is cheap to produce [4].

Currently, they are paying special attention to graphene and its derivatives as a promising material for creating modern technological devices, detectors, fuel cells and renewable energy sources [5]. However, to achieve the desired achievements in the directions indicated above, obtaining graphene and its derivatives in a clean state and environmentally friendly conditions is one of the important issues. To date, many methods of obtaining GO derivatives have been created. For example: the GO synthesis method was developed by chemically reacting KClO_3 and HNO_3 to graphite (Staudenmaier method). In the Hummers method, GO is obtained by oxidizing graphite in the medium of concentrated sulfuric acid and KMnO_4 solutions [6]. In addition, it has been shown that GO can be obtained in K_2FeO_4 and concentrated sulfuric acid [7]. A method for obtaining GO using NaNO_3

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salt, concentrated sulfuric acid and KMnO_4 was developed [8].

Studies on the synthesis of GO of electrochemical methods have also been carried out. For example, it was possible to obtain GO by passing a direct current of 1.6 V from a graphite plate immersed in a 98% sulfuric acid solution as an anode [9].

In 0.5 mol/L $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ solution, a direct current with a voltage of 8~15 V was passed in 1–4 hours through the graphite and cathode platinum electrodes used as an anode, and GO was obtained [10]. GO was synthesized as a result of passing an electric current of 20 V for 20 minutes through graphite electrodes immersed in KClO_3 solution with a concentration of 0.5 mol/L [11].

GO with a C/O ratio of 17.2 was obtained from a 0.1 mol/L K_2SO_4 solution through a graphite foil by passing a direct current at a voltage of 10 V [12]. It has been shown that GO with a thickness of up to 4.49 nm can be obtained by passing a direct current at a voltage of up to 10 V from rod-shaped graphite electrodes immersed in a 0.1 mol/L sodium saccharin solution [13]. GO with a C/O ratio of 36 was obtained by passing a direct current of 20 V through graphite foils in a Na_2SO_4 solution with a concentration of 0.5 mol/L [14]. There is information on the electrochemical synthesis of GO in an HClO_4 solution with a concentration of 8 mol/L [15].

There is information that 0.005, 0.020 and 0.025 g of GO per hour was obtained by passing an electric current of 3, 4.5 and 6 V from graphite electrodes in a solution of sodium dodecylbenzenesulfonate (SDBS) with a concentration of 0.01 mol/L [16].

Experimental studies have been carried out by selecting different values of pH and applied voltage in obtaining GO in H_2SO_4 solution. The pH value of the solution was changed from 1 to 3, and the voltage was changed from 7.5 to 10 V. Experiments were carried out to obtain GO. As a result of research, it was determined that 80.5 mg of GO is formed when an electric current of 8.5 V is passed through graphite electrodes from a solution with a pH of 1. This amount was significantly higher than the amounts of GO obtained under other conditions. In this study, the equation $m(\text{GO}) = -34.68 + 38.50U - 95.30\text{pH} - 6.60U \cdot \text{pH} - 1.32U^2 + 29.43\text{pH}^2$ was proposed to determine the formation mass (mg) of GO according to the actual factors obtained for the model. However, taking into account other factors in the formation of GO, it was shown that the most optimal condition is the voltage of 9.56 V and the pH of the solution 1.29 [17].

We used a new electrochemical method to synthesize GO by passing a direct current through graphite electrodes in a cold solution of ammonium carbonate.

2 Materials and methods

Ammonium carbonate (99.9%, Germany), graphite (99.99%, China), bidistilled water, ice, digital magnetic stirrer hot plate (MS7-H550-S, China), DC power supply with voltage control (~1.5 A, ~15 V, LEYBOLD®, Germany), 4 volumetric flasks with a volume of 50 ml, 2 double-necked round-bottom flasks with a volume of 250 ml, hoses, glass tubes, heat-resistant glasses with a volume of 50 ml, a glass rod. A JASCO FT/IR-4600 spectrometer was used to study IR spectra.

2.2 Electrochemical production of GO from graphite

Ammonium carbonate solutions with a concentration of 0.25, 0.5, 1.0 and 1.5 mol/L were freshly prepared in 50 ml measuring flasks. The resulting solutions were poured into 50 ml beakers, and graphite plates and platinum electrodes were placed in the solutions. First, a direct current of 5, 6, 7 and 8 V was passed through ammonium carbonate solution with a concentration of 0.25 mol/L for 4 hours. The beaker containing the ammonium carbonate solution, which is undergoing electrolysis, was lowered into ice water (12–15°C) and cooled. After removing the electrodes from the solution, the solution in the glass was exposed to 44 kHz ultrasound for 5 minutes. The solution in the beaker was poured into a stirring flask and stirred at a temperature of 80–90°C until ammonium carbonate

disintegrated from the solution. As a result, GO, free of salt ions, remained in the driving flask. In other concentrated solutions, experiments were conducted in the above order.

3 Results and discussions

The advantage of electrochemical synthesizing GO in an ammonium carbonate solution is that hydrogen (H_2) and oxygen (O_2) gases are released during the electrochemical process in this medium. Hydrogen and oxygen gases have no harmful effects on the environment. The resulting GO can be easily and cleanly obtained from the solution. Because ammonium carbonate in the solution decomposes into ammonia (NH_3), carbon dioxide (CO_2) and water under the influence of heat.

The reason for keeping the temperature of the ammonium carbonate solution used for GO synthesis at 12-15°C is to reduce the hydrolysis of ammonium carbonate salt. Because, when the ammonium carbonate solution is hydrolyzed, the amount of ions in the solution decreases, the electrical conductivity also decreases, and at the same time, it hurts the production efficiency of GO. Therefore, the temperature of the ammonium carbonate solution should be cold to efficiently obtain GO.

To synthesize GO electrochemical, experiments were carried out in ammonium carbonate solutions with different concentrations (C) and at different voltages (U). First, a direct current of 5, 6, 7 and 8 V was passed through graphite electrodes from ammonium carbonate solution with a concentration of 0.25 mol/L for 4 hours. The amounts of GO produced as a result of the processes are presented in Figure 1 below.

Fig. 1 Amounts of formation of GO in 0.25 mol/L ammonium carbonate solution by different electric voltages

If we pay attention to the graph, we can observe that the formation amount of GO is anomalously the highest under the influence of 6 V voltage. Therefore, the use of a 6 V electric current to obtain GO in an ammonium carbonate solution with a concentration of 0.25 mol/L leads to efficiency. Further experiments were carried out in other concentrated solutions of ammonium carbonate. Solutions with a concentration of 0.5, 1.0 and 1.5 mol/L were used in the experiments (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2 Amounts of formation of GO in ammonium carbonate solutions with different concentrations (Process time was 4 hours, $U=6$ V)

According to the obtained results, it was found that the formation amount of GO is the highest in ammonium carbonate solution with a concentration of 1 mol/L. At concentrations higher than 1 mol/L, the formation of GO decreased.

Therefore, obtaining GO by passing an electric current at a voltage of 6 V in ammonium carbonate solution with a concentration of 1 mol/L can be considered as the optimal condition.

The composition of GO obtained in ammonium carbonate solution was analyzed using the ATR-FTIR spectroscopy method (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3 ATR-FTIR spectrum of GO

The absorption, 3455 cm^{-1} in the ATR-FTIR spectrum of GO, is characteristic of free -OH groups. Absorption in the region 3200 cm^{-1} is related to the presence of internal hydrogen bonds [18]. It can be considered that -OH groups were formed on the graphene sheet as a result of oxidation under the influence of oxygen in the electrochemical process. Absorption in the region of 1704 cm^{-1} belongs to the carboxyl group [19] and absorption in the region of 1652 cm^{-1} belongs to C=O in the aldehyde group. This means that -COOH and -CHO functional groups were formed on the graphene sheet as a result of oxidation.

The absorption at 3068.7 cm^{-1} in the ATR-FTIR spectrum belongs to the C-H group in the aromatic ring.

Absorption in the area of 2873.7 cm^{-1} is typical for the $-\text{CH}_2-$ group. Absorption in the region of, 1448 cm^{-1} corresponds to the C-H bond in the methyl group. These results indicate that $-\text{CH}_2-$, $-\text{CH}_3$ groups were formed as a result of exposure of the outer parts of the graphene sheet with the hydrogen released in the electrochemical process [20].

Fig. 4 A model of the structure of GO

Absorption in the region of 1316.97 cm^{-1} is related to the C-O bond in aromatic ethers. Based on the above results, it can be concluded that oxidation and reduction of graphene sheets were also observed. The resulting graphene oxide can be seen in the above structure (Figure 4).

To obtain pure GO in solution, it is necessary to get rid of ammonium carbonate salt. For this, an ammonium carbonate solution containing GO was boiled, and the resulting gases were absorbed in cold water. As a result of the dissolution of ammonia and carbon dioxide gases formed from the decomposition of ammonium carbonate in cold water, they again form ammonium carbonate salt and ammonium bicarbonate in solution. These salts can be used again for the synthesis of GO. This method is important because it does not produce waste material.

4 Conclusion

It is necessary to obtain GO by electrochemical method in a cold solution of ammonium carbonate. The solution hurts the production efficiency of GO in the heated case. In the process of synthesis, it was observed that the amount of formation of GO was particularly high at a voltage of 6 V and a solution with a concentration of 1.0 mol/L of ammonium carbonate. When the ammonium carbonate solution containing GO is boiled, GO and water remain in the solution. This situation allowed us to get a clean GO.

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